

Eye-Safe Terabit-Class WDM Optical Wireless: How Many Channels are Enough?

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Abstract: On the path towards Terabit-class optical wireless, the use of WDM technology poses many practical questions. Supported by a 1.8 km field-trial, and multiplexing up to $16 \times 200\text{G}$ channels, we expose the tradeoffs between capacity and reliability depending on the channel count, optical pre-amplification architecture and coding requirements.

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1. Introduction

Fostered by the upcoming 6G revolution, next-generation wireless communications must be ready to break the Terabit-per-second barrier in order to cope with the global network needs. To that end, free-space optics (FSO) is deemed to become a key technology unblocker, owing to its virtually infinite bandwidth and license-free spectrum [1]. Following this challenge, several recent works have initiated the exploitation of multi-wavelength FSO communications, enabling the demonstration of record-high multi-Terabit data-rates [2, 3]. Although these hero experiments confirm the tremendous potential of FSO to provide ultra-high capacity over-the-air, numerous practical issues must be critically addressed before massive deployment. In that regard, a few other recent works have been focusing on the validation of high-capacity FSO systems using commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) optical transceivers, namely resorting to the use of 100G/200G CFP2-DCO coherent pluggables [4]. To scale up the capacity of these systems towards Terabit-per-second and beyond, wavelength-division multiplexing (WDM) is mandatory. However, due to the limited transmitted power imposed by eye-safety regulations, together with the unpredictable time-varying behavior of the free-space channel, the proper dimensioning of these FSO links is non-trivial. In addition, practical engineering issues, such as the use of global or wavelength-dedicated receiver-side optical pre-amplification, must be taken into account.

To address this challenge, let us start from a basic theoretical standpoint, considering the governing Shannon capacity formulation for power-constrained transmission:

$$C = N_{\text{WDM}} B \log_2(1 + \text{SNR}/N_{\text{WDM}}), \quad (1)$$

where N_{WDM} is the number of WDM channels, B is the symbol-rate per channel, and SNR is the signal-to-noise ratio when operating in a single-channel condition. Considering a scenario with 32 Gbaud CFP2-DCO transceivers, Fig. 1.a) depicts the achievable bit-rate (ABR) in an ideal power-constrained WDM system, with an operating SNR of 13 dB. In this hypothetical scenario, a theoretical minimum of 10 WDM channels is required to achieve 1 Tbps. Conversely, Fig. 1.b) shows that a minimum of 8 to 16 WDM channels are required to achieve 1 Tbps for typical SNR values in the range of 12–14 dB. Nevertheless, this theoretical analysis only serves as a bounding box for the expected practical implementation, which introduces numerous non-ideal parameters, such as the impact of bandwidth limitations, suboptimal modulation and/or coding, and the indelible impact of turbulence-induced power fading.

Resorting to a 1.8 km FSO field trial connecting two buildings in the municipality of Aveiro, Portugal, in this work, we explore the appropriate number of 200 Gbps WDM channels that should be transmitted, employing two different pre-amplification methodologies: i) dedicated channel pre-amplification *i.e.* one EDFA pre-amplifier per wavelength; and ii) global signal pre-amplification, *i.e.* only one EDFA pre-amplifier shared by all received wavelengths. Finally, we optimize the forward error correction (FEC) overhead, achieving an effective bit-rate of 820 Gbps with global pre-amplification and 909 Gbps by performing channel-wise pre-amplification.

2. Experimental Setup

The deployed field trial between Instituto de Telecomunicações (IT)-Aveiro and Parque de Ciência e Inovação-Ílhavo (PCI) is depicted in Fig. 2. At the transmitter, standard 200 Gbps signal is generated, with 16-QAM map-

Fig. 1: a) Achievable bit-rate versus number of WDM channels, considering $B = 32$ Gbaud and $\text{SNR} = 13$ dB; b) minimum number of channels required for 1 Tbps transmission versus average SNR.

Fig. 2: Field trial of $N_{\text{WDM}} \times 200$ Gbps coherent transmission over a 1.8 km FSO link between IT-Aveiro and PCI-Ílhavo.

Fig. 3: Measured NGMI for 8–16 WDM channels while employing the different amplification strategies, channel-wise and global.

ping, a symbol-rate of 32 Gbaud, and 20% FEC overhead is generated. The signal undergoes root raised cosine (RRC) pulse-shaping with 0.1 roll-off before being sent to an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG, Keysight M8194A) with 45 GHz bandwidth and 120 Gsps sampling-rate. Then, the electrical signal is optically modulated by a dual-polarization IQ modulator with 35 GHz bandwidth over a WDM signal with 8–16 wavelengths (1535 nm–1545 nm). Afterwards, the modulated signal is sent to free-space by a commercial optical head developed by Aircision. The optical wireless signal travels through a 1.8 km free-space channel and is fiber-coupled by another Aircision optical head. Two approaches are employed to amplify the optical signal: i) channel selection and amplification, and ii) amplification of the WDM signal. In both scenarios, the amplification is performed by an EDFA with automatic power control (APC)¹. However, it is worth noting that in a practical scenario, the first methodology would require N_{WDM} EDFAs (with N_{WDM} being the number of wavelengths transmitted), whereas the second methodology would require one EDFA. Finally, the amplified signal is optical-to-electrical converted by a coherent receiver with 40 GHz bandwidth and quantified and digitized by 4 real-time oscilloscopes (RTO) with 70 GHz and 200 Gsps sampling-rate (Tektronix DPO77002SX-R3). Finally, the digital signal undergoes offline processing with typical coherent DSP techniques, namely: IQ imbalance compensation, 2×2 CMA-based adaptive equalization, frequency and phase recovery, 2×2 LMS equalization, bit decoding, and normalized generalized mutual information (NGMI) [5] assessment. It is important to emphasize that the optical heads from Aircision perform all the beam pointing and tracking, minimizing the impact of the pointing errors in the system. The transmitted beam width and power are considered eye-safe according to IEC 60825-1 [6].

3. Experimental Results

Fig. 3 shows the NGMI performance for all tested sets of wavelengths (8, 10, 12, 14 and 16 channels) over time (40 independent measurements are taken for each wavelength), considering either global (upper rows) or dedicated

¹This EDFA architecture has been shown to present good gains in terms of turbulence-induced power fading [3]

Fig. 4: Impact of the number of WDM channels and FEC overhead in the effective bit-rate, considering channel-wise and global amplification.

(bottom rows) pre-amplification. The presented results were obtained between 6th–7th of February of 2023 and show an apparent gain in employing channel-wise amplification, *i.e.* having an EDFA per optical wavelength. However, for higher WDM channel counts, the disparities between amplification methodologies tend to fade out, which hints that the system becomes highly power-constrained, since the transmitted power has to remain constant regardless of the number of WDM channels, thereby ensuring the eye safety requirements for terrestrial FSO systems. Another key aspect to observe is the difference in performance between channels: in an ideal scenario, the system performance should be essentially frequency-flat; however, due to optical filtering in the FSO optical heads, the side channels are quite penalized, setting a hard limitation to the maximum usable number of channels.

Fig. 4 shows the effective bit-rate achieved for both amplification architectures, changing the number of WDM channels and FEC overhead. As presented in [3], increasing the FEC overhead leads to more robust transmission at the expense of reducing the transmitted information rate ($R_{b,\text{transmitted}}$). In order to capture the tradeoff between capacity and reliability, we evaluate the effective bit-rate *i.e.* $R_{b,\text{effective}} = R_{b,\text{transmitted}} \times \eta$, where η is the transmission reliability. From the obtained results, the following main conclusions can be taken:

- i) contrarily to the theoretical expectations from power-constrained Shannon capacity, we have experimentally observed that the overall system capacity does not monotonically increase with ever-growing number of WDM channels; this behavior can be mainly attributed to two critical practical aspects of the system under test: a) the limited optical bandwidth (less than 10 nm) supported by the optical heads, and b) the limited gain budget provided by the receiver-side pre-amplification stage;
- ii) provided that maximum capacity is required, and to take full advantage of wavelength multiplexing in FSO systems, a dedicated pre-amplifier should be allocated to each optical channel, thus maximizing FSO link budget perceived by each channel individually; in the obtained results, this pre-amplification architecture enabled to achieve the maximum effective bit-rate of 909 Gbps with 10 WDM channels;
- iii) instead, if a simplified receiver architecture is prioritized, the optimization of coding overhead might play a major role in enabling single-EDFA global pre-amplification, thus saving $(N_{\text{WDM}} - 1)$ optical amplifiers: 820 Gbps effective bit-rate has been achieved employing 8 WDM channels with roughly 30% FEC overhead.

4. Conclusions

As part of an FSO field trial conducted over a distance of 1.8 km, in this work, we have experimentally addressed a set of critical design options for Terabit-ready WDM-FSO systems, including the role played by the number of transmitted WDM channels and by the receiver-side optical pre-amplification architecture. While WDM technology will inevitably become instrumental in enabling Terabit-class FSO systems, a careful system design must be taken into account, as the theoretical premises of power-constrained transmission might ultimately collide against a number of system practicalities. In this sense, a mindful optimization of the number of transmitted WDM channels is of utmost importance. Revisiting the initial premise of this paper, before asking “How many channels are enough?”, the leading question should be “How many channels are too many?”. Failing to address this question might lead to utterly power- and capacity-inefficient systems.

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